

STEROID COMPOUNDS. PART VI. SOME EXPERIMENTS TOWARDS THE SYNTHESIS OF 11-KETO STEROIDS

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The base-catalysed condensation of ethyl 4-keto-2:3-dimethylcyclohexene-1-carboxylate with alkyl halide and vinylmethyl ketone has been studied. An extension of this reaction to ethyl 4-keto-3-methyl-2-furylcyclohexene-1-carboxylate to obtain intermediates that could be useful for synthesis of 11-keto steroids broke down because the reaction with vinylmethyl ketone did not yield the desired compound (XVIII).

The present investigation was started in 1951 to find out a convenient method of obtaining the furan derivative (XVIII). This compound being a derivative of furacrylic acid, on the Marckwald cleavage (Marckwald, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2813) could be expected to produce the diketo-dicarboxylic ester (I). The tricyclic compound (II) or its various derivatives like (III) could be easily obtained from the above ester (I) and these intermediates could then be profitably utilised for the synthesis of 11-keto steroids. The synthetic approach appeared to be of great promise, provided that a convenient synthesis of the furan derivative (XVIII) could be found. Although our attempts to obtain it were unsuccessful, the results have been of some interest in other respects.

Of the several possibilities to synthesise (XVIII) that were considered, the base-catalysed condensation of vinylmethyl ketone with ethyl 4-keto-3-methyl-2-furyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (VII) appeared to be one of most promise. The anion derived from this compound could react at either of the positions 1 or 3, to furnish (IX) or the bicyclic compound (XVIII; R' = Et) via the intermediate diketone (XIII). The compound (VII) is a vinylogous β -keto-ester and closely related to Hagemann's ester (IV). It has been well established that alkylation of Hagemann's ester takes place at the position 3, next to the keto group (Smith and Rouault, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 631; Horning *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 71, 1771). This is what one would expect in a compound of this structure; for in the mesomeric anion derived from it, reaction is most likely to take place at position-3 which is not substituted compared to position-1, carrying a substituent. The same situation, however, does not obtain in the compounds (V) and (VII) where both the positions 1 and 3 carry substituents. A mixture of products derived from condensation at both the positions could be expected in any base-catalysed reaction. However, the keto group being somewhat more electron-withdrawing, compared to the ester group, it was thought that in the mesomeric anion, derived from such a system, the electron density would be higher in the vicinity of the keto group (Birch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1551, 2325) and the product derived from reaction at position-3 would very likely predominate in the mixture. As far as could be found in literature, there are no reports on reactions of compounds of this type (V and VII).

A preliminary study with the readily available derivative, ethyl 4-keto-2:3-dimethyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (V), was therefore undertaken. An examination of the structure of the two possible compounds that could arise from it reveals that

the compound derived from reaction at position-3 will no longer be a vinylogous β -keto-ester in contrast to the other isomer derived from reaction at position-1, where the vinylogous β -keto-ester system will prevail. By suitable treatments, *i.e.* hydrolysis followed by decarboxylation, such mixtures can be easily separated into acidic and neutral components. Reaction of the above ester (V) with methyl iodide in presence of potassium *tert.*-butoxide in *tert.*-butyl alcohol was very rapid and practically over at room temperature. The crude reaction product was hydrolysed with dilute KOH solution and the total acidic material decarboxylated by heating with dilute HCl. The resulting mixture could be separated into two portions, one acidic and the other neutral, in almost equal amounts. The neutral fraction was a colorless mobile liquid with a very strong ketonic smell, which readily furnished a semicarbazone, m. p. 210° and a red 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m. p. 165° . It can be best represented as 2:3:4-trimethyl Δ^2 -cyclohexenone (XIV). The acidic portion was initially obtained as a gum which soon solidified, and after purification had m. p. 120° . The corresponding methyl ester (XIa) was characterised by a semicarbazone, m. p. 143.5° . The acid can be best represented as 4-keto-2:3:3-trimethylcyclohexene-1-carboxylic acid (XI).

The next reaction studied was the condensation of the potassium enolate of (V) with vinylmethyl ketone. The crude reaction product was treated as described in the previous case and separated into acidic and neutral components in almost equal amounts. The acid (m. p. 162° ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 234μ ; ϵ , 20,000; bands at 5.9μ and 6.0μ in the infra-red) can be best represented as (XVII). The corresponding methyl ester (XVIIa, b. p. $135^\circ/0.2 \text{ mm.}$, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 234μ ; ϵ , 14,000; bands at 5.8μ and 6.0μ in the infra-red) was characterised by a semicarbazone, m. p. 214° and a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m. p. $149-50^\circ$. The maxima at 234μ in the ultraviolet is due to the combined effect of the two chromophoric systems present in the compound.

The neutral fraction with a very strong ketonic smell could be obtained as a low melting crystalline solid (m. p. 44° ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 296μ ; ϵ , 24,400). It was characterised by a semicarbazone, m. p. 233° and a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m. p. 215° . Its structure was proved by reduction with lithium aluminium hydride, followed by dehydrogenation with 10% Pd—C, when 1:7-dimethylnaphthalene, identified through its picrate (Barnett and Sanders, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 437; Darzen and Heinz, *Compt. rend.*, 1927, 184, 33), was obtained. The ketone has therefore been assigned the structure (XV) and is derived from reaction at position-1 to furnish the intermediate (VIII) which undergoes ring-closure between the carbonyl group of the side chain and the β -methyl group on the ring, which is activated by the keto group through the double bond. A somewhat remote possibility that the ketone has the structure (XVI), derived from reaction at the methylene position next to the keto group, is eliminated by synthesis of an authentic specimen of (XVI) and direct comparison with the above ketone. The results from the two foregoing cases definitely establish that the reaction with (V) occurs at the two possible positions and almost equivalent amounts of the two products are obtained.

Ethyl 4-keto-3-methyl-2-furyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (VII) was prepared in the following way. Ethyl 2-furoylacetate (Barger, Robinson and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*,

1937, 721) was condensed with vinylmethyl ketone in presence of catalytic amount of sodium ethoxide to yield the aldol (XLX), which on further treatment with sodium ethoxide could be dehydrated to the Hagemann's ester analogue, ethyl 4-keto-2-furyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (VI). Methylation of this in presence of sodium ethoxide furnished the required compound (VII). Both these compounds were characterised by preparation of their solid derivatives. Condensation of (VII) with vinylmethyl ketone under a variety of conditions afforded a thick, yellow, viscous liquid which never solidified. This material had $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 321 m μ , and nothing around 240 m μ that could be expected if the desired compound (XVIII: R' = Et) was present. Purification by the method worked out in the previous case could not be applied here due to the presence of acid-sensitive grouping (XX) in both the expected isomers. Hydrolysis of the condensation product with 10% KOH was remarkably sluggish, suggesting tertiary character of the ester group. From the resulting gummy product could be isolated only one crystalline acid (m. p. 233° with decomposition; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 323 m μ ; ϵ , 24,000). The analysis agreed with the formula C₁₆H₁₈O₅ that corresponded with the structure (X). When the acid was slowly heated at its melting point, complete decarboxylation occurred to furnish a neutral gum which in the infra-red spectra showed very strong bands at 5.84 μ and 6.0 μ , confirming the presence of saturated and conjugated carbonyl groups in the system. All these observations agree with the structure (X) for this compound. No other acidic material could be isolated and the crude gummy residue, left after removal of the above crystalline acid, also did not show any absorption around 240 m μ region in the ultraviolet. It is somewhat interesting to observe that in the furan derivative reaction occurred exclusively at the 1-position in contrast to the mixture that was obtained in the case of the simpler analogue (V). This specificity suggests that in the transition stage conjugation of the furan ring with the keto group through the double bond is favoured over the *cis*-furanacrylic system, and this could be due to the increased resonance stability in the former system. A number of analogous derivatives are now being studied to evaluate this point more thoroughly.

After this work had been completed, a report on the alkylation of ethyl 4-keto-2 : 3-dimethyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (V) was published by Dyer, Kidd and Walker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4778). The above authors claimed that in presence of sodium methoxide in dry ether the above compound condensed with *p*-cyanobenzyl bromide to afford exclusively 1-(*p*-cyanobenzyl)-4-keto-2 : 3-dimethyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (XXI). This is contrary to our results. The English workers argued that for Hagemann's ester (IV), *Form A* would be favoured by hyperconjugation and that this was in line with the fact that the first stage alkylation of Hagemann's ester occurred at the position next to the keto group, viz., position 3. For the dimethyl compound (V), they argued that hyperconjugation would favour the *Form B* as the more stable form, and hence alkylation would take place next to the carbethoxy group, position-1. These arguments are, however, not quite convincing. Moreover, the experiments described in this communication very clearly demonstrate that in contrast to the highly selective alkylation in Hagemann's ester, a mixture of products has always been obtained in the alkylation of methyl Hagemann's ester (V).

On the basis of their rather fallacious arguments, Walker *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) assigned the structure (XXI) to their product, which they thought was formed exclusively. This appears to be rather unlikely, particularly in the light of the present work, unless the alkylation with cyanobenzyl bromides is peculiar by themselves. It is very likely that they were handling a mixture of products derived from alkylation at both the reactive centres rather than a single pure compound of the assigned structure (XXI). In the light of the present work the above conclusion appears to be inescapable, and, in fact, some of the observations recorded by Walker *et al.* can be better accounted for on the basis of the above hypothesis. A careful reinvestigation of their work is highly desirable and will be reported in a subsequent communication. Further work on the chemistry of mesomeric anions derived from compounds of the type (XXII) is being continued.

(A)

(B)

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV) : R = Me ; R' = H.

(V) : R = R' = Me.

(VI) : R = Furyl ; R' = H.

(VII) : R = Furyl ; R' = Me.

(XXII) : R = Substituent ;
R' = Me.

(VIII) : R = Me , R' = Et ;

R'' = γ -keto-butyl.

(IX) : R = Furyl ; R' = Et ;

R'' = γ -keto-butyl.

(X) : R = Furyl ; R' = H ;

R'' = γ -keto-butyl.

(XI) : R = R'' = Me ; R' = H.

(XIa) : R = R' = R'' = Me.

(XII) : R = Me ; R' = Et ;

R'' = γ -keto-butyl.

(XIII) : R = Furyl ; R' = Et ;

R'' = γ -keto-butyl.

(XIV)

(XV)

(XVI)

(XVII): R = Me; R' = H.

(XVIIa): R = R' = Me.

(XVIII): R = Furyl; R' = H.

(XVIIIa): R = Furyl; R' = Me.

(XIX)

(XX)

(XXI)

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 4-Keto-2:3-dimethyl-Δ²-cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (V). — Ethyl 4-keto-2-methylcyclohexene-1-carboxylate, Hagemann's ester (36.4 g.), was added with stirring to an ice-cold solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (4.7 g.) and absolute alcohol (150 c. c.). After stirring for about 30 minutes, methyl iodide (30.0 g.) was added all at once. After stirring for 2 hours at this temperature, the solution was gradually heated to its boiling point and gently refluxed for one hour. A fresh addition of methyl iodide (15.0 g.) was made and the reflux continued until the solution was neutral to litmus. Excess of alcohol was then removed under reduced pressure, water added and the oil taken up in ether. After washing the ether extract twice with water, it was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the solvent removed and the residual oil distilled, b. p. 105-106°/2 mm., yield 34 g. The above procedure is a definite improvement over the previous published methods (Bergmann and Weizmann, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1939, 4, 267; Smith and Rouault, *loc. cit.*). The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual way, after one crystallisation from alcohol had m. p. 206°. (Found: C, 57.16; H, 7.53. C₁₂H₁₈O₃N₂ requires C, 56.91; H, 7.51 per

cent). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from alcohol in reddish flakes, m. p. 133° (Found: C, 54.40; H, 5.34. $C_{17}H_{20}O_6N_4$ requires C, 54.25; H, 5.31 per cent).

Methylation of Ethyl 4-Keto-2:3-dimethyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate.—The above keto-ester (15 g.) was added to a solution of potassium *tert.*-butoxide, under nitrogen, prepared from potassium (3.2 g.) and *tert.*-butyl alcohol (100 c. c.). The solution turned deep red and after about 30 minutes the insoluble potassium salt separated. This was then cooled in ice and methyl iodide (12.0 g.) was added and the mixture left overnight under nitrogen, by which time the reaction was almost complete. A further addition of methyl iodide (6.0 g.) was made, the mixture gently refluxed for 2 hours, then concentrated under reduced pressure and poured into water. The precipitated oil was extracted with ether and the ether extract after washing with water was dried and concentrated. The residual oil distilled at 105-107°/1.5 mm. as a colorless mobile oil. The above oil was next hydrolysed with 10% alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (from KOH, 7.5 g.) under nitrogen for 6 hours. After removing most of the solvent the dirty brown residue was dissolved in water and extracted with ether. On removal of the ether no residue was left.

2:3:4-Trimethyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone (XIV).—The aqueous alkaline solution from above on being carefully acidified with HCl (dil.) with ice-cooling left a gummy acid. This was taken up in ether. The gummy acid left on removal of the ether was heated in an atmosphere of nitrogen with 10% HCl (50 c. c.), when a vigorous gas evolution started. The heating was continued until no further gas was evolved. After cooling, the solution was repeatedly extracted with ether. The ether extract was then washed several times with portions of dilute sodium bicarbonate solution until no more acidic material could be extracted. After washing finally with water, the ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether carefully removed. The residual oil distilled at 95-98°/16 mm. as colorless oil, yield 4 g. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 244 μ ; ϵ , 13200. (Found: C, 78.04; H, 10.18. $C_9H_{14}O$ requires C, 78.26; H, 10.14 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from ethanol in shining needles, m. p. 210°. (Found: C, 61.13; H, 8.64. $C_{10}H_{17}ON_3$ requires C, 78.26; H, 10.14 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as vermilion-red small needles which after crystallisation from a large volume of alcohol had m. p. 165°. (Found: C, 56.67; H, 5.76. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4N_4$ requires C, 56.60; H, 5.66 per cent).

4-Keto-2:3:3-trimethyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylic Acid (XI).—The sodium bicarbonate extract, obtained above, was cooled in ice and carefully acidified with HCl (dil.). A brown gummy acid was precipitated. This was extracted with ether in the usual way, the ether removed and the residual crude acid (8.0 g.) dried. On trituration with a little ethyl acetate the gum solidified. The crystalline acid was filtered and recrystallised twice from ethyl acetate-petrol ether mixture, m. p. 120°. (Found: C, 66.27; H, 7.87. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.93; H, 7.68 per cent). The crude gummy acid left after removal of the crystalline acid was esterified with anhydrous methanol (70 c. c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 4 c. c.) for 12 hours. The ester (XIa) was

isolated in the usual way and purified by distillation, b. p. 125-27°/10 mm. (Found : C, 67.93 ; H, 8.08. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 67.34 ; H, 8.16 per cent).

The semicarbazone of the ester, prepared in the usual way, was crystallised twice from very dilute methanol in silky needles, m. p. 143.5°. (Found : C, 57.24 ; H, 7.54. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires C, 56.91 ; H, 7.5 per cent).

*Condensation of Ethyl 4-Keto-2:3-dimethyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate
with Methylvinyl Ketone*

A mixture of the keto-ester (39.3 g.) and methylvinyl ketone (15.5 g.) was added to an ice-cold solution of potassium *tert.*-butoxide under nitrogen, prepared from potassium (1.1 g.) and *tert.*-butyl alcohol (80 c.c.), when a deep red solution was obtained which was left overnight at room temperature under nitrogen. It was then acidified with the calculated amount of acetic acid and poured into water. The precipitated heavy oil was isolated by ether extraction and the extract was washed successively with water, 10% sodium carbonate solution and again with water. After drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the solvent was removed and the residual oil distilled, when two distinct fractions could be separated : (a) b.p. 100°-130°/0.2 mm., 13 g. (b) b. p. 140°-160°/0.2 mm., 20 g. There was a high boiling polymeric residue in the distillation flask.

The first fraction on redistillation boiled at 105°-108°/0.15 mm. and was the unchanged keto-ester.

The second fraction on redistillation boiled at 147°-152°/0.15 mm. as a mobile pale yellow liquid. The distillate had $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 242 m μ (ϵ , 8210; but the maxima was somewhat diffused indicating non-homogeneity).

The above condensation product (29 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing under nitrogen with KOH (30 g.), water (30 c. c.) and methanol (250 c. c.). The alcohol was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in water. This aqueous solution was then extracted with several portions of ether to remove neutral matter, if any present. But on working up the extract no organic residue was obtained.

2-Keto-1:7-dimethyl- $\Delta^{1:7}$ -hexahydronaphthalene (XV).—The solution from the above operation was then acidified with ice-cooling and the gummy acid extracted with several portions of ether, and the ether distilled off. The residue was then heated under nitrogen with water (300 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 100 c. c.) when a brisk gas evolution started. Heating was continued until this gas evolution was complete, which required about 30 to 40 minutes. After cooling, the aqueous solution was extracted with ether and the ether layer washed several times with small portions of 10% sodium bicarbonate solution until no more acidic matter could be extracted. The neutral ether extract on evaporation afforded a pale yellow mobile oil with a characteristic ketonic smell, which distilled at 114-16°/0.7 mm., as a colorless mobile liquid, yield 8.0 g. This oil on keeping gradually solidified and after two crystallisations from ether-petrol ether mixture had m. p. 44°; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 296 m μ ; ϵ , 24, 400. (Found : C, 81.87 ; H, 9.4. $C_{12}H_{16}O$ requires C, 81.8 ; H, 9.09 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, which formed very readily, was crystallised from a large volume of alcohol, m. p. 233°. (Found: C, 66.86; H, 8.13. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_3$ requires C, 66.95; H, 8.15 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as deep red flakes from chloroform-alcohol mixture, m. p. 215°. (Found: C, 60.30; H, 5.74. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4N_4$ requires C, 60.67; H, 5.61 per cent).

The above ketone was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and the crude alcohol was dehydrogenated with 10% Pd—C initially at 220° and finally at 280°, over a period of about 1½ hours. The reaction product was isolated in the usual way and purified by distilling over metallic sodium. The distillate with a characteristic naphthalene odour instantly formed a picrate which after one crystallisation from alcohol was obtained as lemon-yellow needles, m. p. 120-21°, unaltered by repeated crystallisation. Lit. reports m. p. 120° (Barnett and Sanders, *loc. cit.* Darzens and Heinz, *loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 55.72; H, 4.21. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{15}O_7N_2$: C, 56.10; H, 3.90 per cent).

6-Keto-1:9-dimethyl- $\Delta^1:5:10$ -hexahydronaphthalene-2-carboxylic Acid (XVII).—The aqueous alkaline solution was acidified with ice-cooling and the gummy precipitate extracted with ether. After washing with two portions of water, it was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The residual gum (12 g.) slowly crystallised. Direct crystallisation of the crude acid to obtain pure sample was extremely difficult due to contamination of some polymeric material. Hence, it was esterified with methanol and sulphuric acid in the usual way and the ester purified by distillation, b. p. 135°/0.2 mm. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 234 m μ ; ϵ , 14,000. (Found: C, 71.35; H, 8.07. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 71.8; H, 7.69 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was very readily obtained and after one crystallisation from methyl alcohol had m. p. 214°. (Found: C, 61.96; H, 7.36. $C_{15}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires C, 61.93; H, 7.21 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from methyl alcohol-chloroform mixture in orange-red flakes, m. p. 149-50°; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 389 m μ ; ϵ , 32,400. (Found: C, 58.38; H, 5.53. $C_{20}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires C, 57.97; H, 5.31 per cent).

The acid was readily obtained pure by hydrolysis of the above ester with 10% alcoholic KOH, followed by isolation in the usual way. The keto-acid was crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and methanol, m. p. 162°. (Found: C, 70.90; H, 7.43. $C_{13}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 70.91; H, 7.27 per cent).

7-Keto-1:2-dimethyl- $\Delta^1:8$ -hexahydronaphthalene (XVI).—A mixture of 2:3-dimethylcyclohexenone (15 g.) and ethyl formate (18 g.) was added to a suspension of dry sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium (5.5 g.), suspended in anhydrous benzene (150 c. c.) under nitrogen. The whole mixture was cooled in ice during addition. The reaction mixture was left overnight under nitrogen. The resulting cake of sodium salt was then decomposed with water and the benzene layer removed. The alkaline solution was then just acidified with dilute acetic acid and the precipitated oil extracted with ether. On removal of the ether, a brown oil (15 g.) was obtained. This crude formyl ketone (15 g.) and methylvinyl ketone (7.0 g.) in *tert.*-butyl alcohol (25 c. c.) were cooled in ice under nitrogen and a solution of potassium *tert.*-butoxide from potassium (0.6 g.)

in *tert.*-butyl alcohol (25 c. c.) was added. After allowing it to stand overnight, the reaction mixture was poured into water, and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with dilute alkali solution and water, and dried. The residual crude condensation product (18 g.), left after removal of the ether, was directly cyclised in the following way.

The crude product (18 g.) in dioxan (375 c. c.) was cooled in ice and to this was added an ice-cold solution of KOH (15 g.) in water (375 c. c.). The addition was done under nitrogen and the mixture was left at room temperature overnight. It was then diluted with water and extracted with several portions of ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dilute acid solution, again with water, and finally dried. The oil remaining after removal of the ether distilled at 110-112°/0.3 mm. as a colorless mobile oil with a characteristic smell. This ketone gradually solidified and after two crystallisations from ether-petroleum ether mixture had m. p. 45.5°. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 296 m μ ; ϵ , 24,700. (Found: C, 81.4; H, 9.12. C₁₅H₁₆(^o) requires C, 81.8; H, 9.09 per cent).

The *stemicarbazone* was phototropic and gradually turned yellow, m. p. 237° (Found: C, 67.02; H, 8.17. C₁₅H₁₅(O)N₂ requires C, 66.95; H, 8.15 per cent).

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as deep red flakes, m. p. 213.5°. (Found: C, 60.77; H, 5.90. C₁₈H₂₀(4)N₄ requires C, 60.67; H, 5.61 per cent).

Ethyl 4-Keto-2-furyl 2-hydroxycyclohexane-1-carboxylate (XIX).—A mixture of ethyl 2-furoylacetate (4.6 g.) and methylvinyl ketone (2.0 g.) was added to an ice-cold solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.06 g.) and absolute alcohol (10.0 c. c.), under nitrogen. The mixture was allowed to warm up to room temperature and left overnight under nitrogen. The resulting solid cake was decomposed with ether and water; the aqueous layer was extracted twice with ether and the combined ether extract was washed with water, 10% sodium bicarbonate solution, again with water, and finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The viscous residue, left after removal of the ether, very readily solidified. This was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether (b.p. 30°-60°), m. p. 97°, yield 5.1 g. The compound was recrystallised once from the same solvent and was obtained in fine silky needles, m. p. 98°. (Found: C, 61.93; H, 6.34. C₁₈H₁₆O₅ requires C, 61.9; H, 6.35 per cent).

Ethyl 4-Keto-2-furylcyclohexene-1-carboxylate (VI).—(a). The above crystalline aldol (5.0 g.), dissolved in dry benzene (25 c. c.), was added to a solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.12 g.) and alcohol (20 c. c.). The mixture was left overnight at room temperature under nitrogen. Next day it was refluxed on a steam-bath under nitrogen for 1½ hours. It was then cooled and poured into cold water containing the calculated amount of acetic acid. The organic layer was removed, the aqueous solution was twice extracted with ether and the combined organic extract was then washed with water, 10% sodium bicarbonate solution, again with water, and finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the ether, a pale brown viscous oil was left, which distilled at 148°-152°/0.6 mm. as a pale yellow somewhat viscous oil (3.5 g.). This was redistilled and a fraction boiling at 125°/0.1 mm. was collected for analysis. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 318 m μ ; ϵ , 22,500. (Found: C, 67.00; H, 6.66. C₁₅H₁₄O₄ requires C, 66.67; H, 6.0 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was deep red in colour and after crystallisation from alcohol-chloroform mixture had m. p. 138°. (Found : C, 55.25 ; H, 4.38. $C_{19}H_{11}O_7N_4$ requires C, 55.06 ; H, 4.55 per cent).

The semicarbazone after crystallisation from alcohol had m. p. 178°. It was phototropic and readily turned yellow. (Found : C, 57.67 ; H, 5.94. $C_{11}H_{17}O_4N_3$ requires C, 57.72 ; H, 5.84 per cent).

(b). While working with larger quantities it was found unnecessary to isolate the intermediate aldol and the following procedure provided satisfactory results. The mixture of β -keto-ester (148 g.) and methylvinyl ketone (68 g.) was added to an ice-cold sodium ethoxide solution (from sodium, 3.2 g. and alcohol, 100 c. c.) under nitrogen. After allowing it to stand at room temperature overnight, a solution of sodium ethoxide from sodium (2.5 g.) and alcohol (200 c. c.) was added, followed by dry benzene (300 c. c.). The whole mixture was refluxed in an atmosphere under nitrogen for about 3 hours, cooled, poured into acidulated water and worked up as before. The product distilled at 158°-162°/1.0 mm., yield 120 g.

Ethyl 4-Keto-3-methyl-2-furyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (VII).—The foregoing keto-ester (VI, 21 g.) was added with stirring to an ice-cold solution of sodium ethoxide from sodium (2.1 g.) and absolute alcohol (80 c. c.), kept under nitrogen. A reddish brown solution was obtained. Methyl iodide (28.0 g.) was added and stirring continued at this temperature for 1½ hours. The mixture was then refluxed on the steam-bath for another 2 hours, when the solution became neutral to litmus and only pale yellow in colour. Alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and to the residue water was added and then extracted with ether. The ether extract was then processed in the usual way and evaporated. The residual oil was distilled, b.p. 150-52°/0.7 mm., yield 18 g.

For analytical sample a small portion was redistilled, b. p. 123-25°/0.2 mm. $\lambda_{max}^{alcohol}$, 318 m μ ; ϵ , 23,450. (Found : C, 67.70 ; H, 6.42. $C_{14}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 67.73 ; H, 6.45 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as very dark reddish flakes, m. p. 140°. (Found : C, 55.66 ; H, 4.67. $C_{20}H_{20}O_7N_4$ requires C, 56.08 ; H, 4.67 per cent).

The semicarbazone, which was phototropic, gradually changed to yellow, m. p. 191 (Found : C, 59.01 ; H, 6.28. $C_{15}H_{19}O_4N_3$ requires C, 59.01 ; H, 6.23 per cent).

*Condensation of Ethyl 4-Keto-3-methyl-2-furylcyclohexene-1-carboxylate (VII)
with Methylvinyl Ketone*

A mixture of the ester (20 g.) and methylvinyl ketone (6.5 g.) in dry ether (300 c. c.) was added with efficient stirring to an ice-cold solution of potassium *tert.*-butoxide, prepared from potassium (0.5 g.) and *tert.*-butyl alcohol (60 c. c.), under nitrogen. A purple colour soon developed which gradually turned dark red. After allowing it to stand overnight at room temperature, the dark viscous reaction mixture was poured into water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution, several times with water, finally dried and the solvent removed. The residual brown oil was then distilled from a short-path distilling flask. After an initial

forerun of the starting material (10.0 g.), distilling between 140° and 170°/0.2 mm. (bath temp.), a highly viscous oil distilled at 180°-210°/0.2 mm. (bath temp.). This was again redistilled and the major fraction distilling at 180°-190°/0.2 mm. was collected (10 g.). A considerable amount of a high boiling residue was left in the flask. The distillate had $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 321 m μ ; ϵ , 12,000. In spite of repeated fractionations a purer specimen could not be obtained and the distillate was always contaminated with some non-absorbing material. For the same reason an analytical sample could not be collected and no solid derivative could be prepared. The distillate which was obtained as a pale yellow gum gradually turned brown and after several days completely turned black. Several experiments on the hydrolysis of the above distillate with alkali showed that the ester group was somewhat strongly hindered. The compound (10 g.) was refluxed under nitrogen for 10 hours with a solution, prepared from potassium hydroxide pellets (8.6 g.), water (8.6 c.c.) and methanol (86 c.c.). At the end of this period, the solution was concentrated under reduced pressure and then poured into water. The aqueous solution was extracted three times with ether and after usual processing, the ether was removed leaving a brown gum (7 g.) whose infra-red spectrum was identical with that of the starting material. The alkaline solution was carefully acidified when a dark brown gummy acid precipitated. This was isolated by extracting with ether. The product (3 g.) left after removal of the ether on trituration with dry ether partly solidified. The crystalline acid had m. p. 228-29° (decomp.). The gum remaining after removal of the above crystalline acid resisted all attempts at crystallisation.

The recovered neutral material (6 g.) was again hydrolysed with KOH (3.5 g.), water (3.5 c.c.) and methyl alcohol (35 c.c.). The neutral portion (about 4 g.) was removed in the usual way and the acid was isolated as before. This acidic product (1.5 g.) was relatively pure and completely crystallised. The crude acid had m. p. 229° (decomp.) and after two crystallisations from ethyl acetate and benzene containing some methanol it could be obtained pure as colorless thick needles, m. p. 233° (decomp.). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 323 m μ ; ϵ , 21,000. (Found: C, 66.12, 65.84; H, 6.39, 6.19. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 66.20; H, 6.21 per cent).

Attempts to prepare derivatives of this acid were not successful. Several attempts for the oxidation of this acid with sodium hypobromite and hypoiodide were also unsuccessful. The pure crystalline acid (200 mg.) was slowly heated to its melting point and maintained at that temperature. The crystals melted, followed by gas evolution. After the gas evolution had completely ceased, the residual brown gum was taken up in ether and the extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and the ether removed. The remaining brown liquid had sharp bands at 5.84 μ and 6.05 μ in the infra-red.

The above acid (1 g.) in ether solution was esterified with the calculated amount of diazomethane. The methyl ester obtained, after removal of the unchanged acid by alkali washing and subsequent evaporation of ether, was an almost colorless viscous oil; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alcohol}}$, 321 m μ .

The above crude ester, dissolved in ethyl alcohol (10 c.c.), was added to an ice-cooled solution of sodium borohydride (0.2 g.) in ethyl alcohol (10 c.c.) and left overnight. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with calculated amount of acetic acid and the alcohol removed under reduced pressure. The organic matter was extracted with ether and on removal of the solvent a brown brittle glass was obtained. This had no band at 6.05μ in the infra-red and had $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alcohol}}, 260\text{m}\mu$.

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